

Synthetic methanol for shipping decarbonisation

COP FRAMEWORK

Deliverable D2.1

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CHANGE CONTROL

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report presents the general framework of the communities of practices (COP) to be established at both use case level in Thessaloniki and Valencia to support the implementation of new value chains based on e-methanol for shipping. This framework describes the main rules to be followed to run the communities and ensure sustained members' engagement from project start to finish and beyond. The results presented here are based on a collaborative work involving the Greek and Spanish project partners of POSEIDON and external stakeholders who provided feedback through workshops. The methodology to develop the COP framework was guided by “The Communities of Practice Playbook”, a document and toolbox developed by the EU commission to run and develop communities. This report is organized as follows:

- Short introduction – [Introduction](#),
- General information about COP – [Chapter 2](#),
- The two use cases of POSEIDON - [Chapter 3](#),
- Purpose of COPs within POSEIDON – [Chapter 4](#),
- Workshops to develop COP framework -[Chapter 5](#),
- Main conclusions including presentation of the general COP framework within POSEIDON - [Conclusion](#).

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
AAPA	American Association of Port Authorities
AIVP	International Association of Cities and Ports
CMF	Clean Marine Fuel
COP	Community of Practice
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
ESPO	European Sea Ports Organisation
GHG	Greenhouse Gas

IAPH	International Association of Ports and Harbors
IMO	International Maritime Organization
PIANC	World Association for Waterborne Transport Infrastructure
RLCF	Renewable and Low-Carbon Fuels
WP	Work Package
WPSP	World Ports Sustainability Program

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the objectives of POSEIDON is to set up communities of practice (COP) in Valencia and Thessaloniki to prepare the implementation of local value chains based on e-methanol as fuel for shipping. These communities will consist of local project partners from Greece and Spain and relevant stakeholders of the value chain that would like to be actively involved in the creation of new value chains to boost the use of e-methanol. These working groups will both learn from the project and support the co-development of results: project partners will provide trainings to support capacity building of COP members on the topic of renewable marine fuels and COP members will contribute to the development and validation of local roadmaps and policy recommendations to efficiently prepare the future deployment of e-methanol technologies in shipping.

To establish COPs, it is necessary to have a general framework on how to run the COPs and keep people engaged from project start to project end and beyond. The development of this general framework is based on a guidebook from the European Commission and the inputs of the Spanish and Greek POSEIDON project partners and external stakeholders gathered through workshops. Readers of this deliverable should note that COPs are living communities and therefore the framework presented in this document is susceptible to evolve in the course of the project as more feedback will be collected. It will be key to make COPs attractive platforms for knowledge exchange and co-creation, so that the expected project impacts can be reached. A report of all COP activities (D2.9) will be submitted towards the end of the project.

2 COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE - COP

2.1 DEFINITION

A COP is a group of people who share a same concern, an interest in a topic and come together to address both individual and common objectives. COPs often focus on sharing best practices and creating new knowledge or advance a domain of professional practice. Many COPs rely on face-to-face meetings as well as web-based collaborations to connect, communicate and perform community activities.

Cognitive anthropologists Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger defined the term when studying apprenticeships as learning models. A lot of people have learned together through informal communities of practice¹.

There are three main characteristics of COP:

¹ M. K. Smith, "Communities of practice", <https://infed.org/mobi/jean-lave-etienne-wenger-and-communities-of-practice/>, last accessed February 2024;

1. Domain: community members share a same domain of interest and competence that guides their learning and commitment,
2. Community: members pursue this interest by networking, joint activities, sharing knowledge,
3. Practice: members are practitioners and build a shared repertoire of resources and ideas².

Figure 1: The main characteristics of COPs (taken from Jean Lave and Etienne Wenger)

In contrast to other organizational structures such as teams or task forces focusing on a project or a specific function which tend to disperse when a task is accomplished, a COP provides strategic capability gained through continuous learning that can benefit the organisations in which its members work. It is this ongoing learning that bound COP members and give them the commitment to remain involved in the community³.

2.2 GENERAL PRUPOSE OF IMPLEMENTING COP IN RESEARCH PROJECTS

Research has shown^{4 5} that connecting people with different backgrounds together can have great impact on the use and implementation of new innovative solutions at local level and on the subsequent diffusion to other locations. Communities of practice are particularly relevant in international collaborative projects where the technologies developed will affect the current practices and relationships of key stakeholders. They will facilitate knowledge exchange between partners, foster capacity building of the members and support co-creation by a diverse group of individuals. This will support the long-term success of innovations developed and tested in project case studies.

² E. Wenger-Trayner & B. Wenger-Trayner, “Introduction to Communities of Practice”, <http://wenger-trayner.com/introduction-to-communities-of-practice/>, last accessed October 2023

³ E. Wenger-Trayner, B. Wenger-Trayner et al., „Communities of practice within and across organisations – a guidebook (2nd edition)”, <https://www.wenger-trayner.com/cop-guidebook/>, last accessed February 2024

⁴ K. Garrety et al., “Integrating communities of practice in technology development projects”, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0263786303000917>, last accessed February 2024

⁵ M. Bettiol & S. R. Sedita, “The role of community of practice in developing creative industry projects”; <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0263786311000081>; last accessed February 2024

2.3 RATIONALE OF IMPLEMENTING COPS IN POSEIDON

The choice to establish COPs in Valencia and Thessaloniki is because successful implementation of new value chains can only be realized when key stakeholders are involved in the process, share their thoughts, learn from each other, and co-create and validate some key results such as implementation scenarios and the local deployment roadmap. The COPs set up within POSEIDON will help in building trust in this transformation process and in preparing the future implementation of the value chains in Thessaloniki and Valencia.

2.4 WORKING GROUPS DEDICATED TO THE TOPIC OF ALTERNATIVE FUELS

According to quick internet search carried out by partner Steinbeis, there is no community of practice at port, country, EU or world level that is dedicated to the topic of renewable alternative fuels. However, there are several working groups, associations, class societies and alliances that work on this topic and try to co-develop solutions that can help stakeholders start their own transitions. A non-exhaustive list of the main international working groups is presented in the following.

Sustainable Marine Fuels group of the World Ports Sustainability Program

In May 2017, the International Association of Ports and Harbors (IAPH) set up the World Ports Sustainability Program (WPSP), as a global effort to coordinate sustainability actions of ports worldwide and foster international cooperation. Strategic partners such as the American Association of Port Authorities (AAPA), the European Sea Ports Organisation (ESPO), the International Association of Cities and Ports (AIVP) and the World Association for Waterborne Transport Infrastructure (PIANC) joined the programme⁶.

Working group 4 of the WPSP is dedicated to sustainable marine fuels. Its goal is to help accelerate the use of sustainable low carbon fuels in marine transport by facilitating the test of these fuels in inland, coastal and sea-going vessels, by raising awareness of these fuels by sharing information and documenting lessons learned and developing guidance documents and by collaborating with industry and government to make sustainable fuels viable in the long run. The working group consists of the following members: port of Antwerp, port of Barcelona, port of Gothenburg, Hamburg port authority, port of Le Havre, port of New York & New Jersey, port of Rotterdam, port of Vancouver, port of Yokohama⁷.

Clean Marine Fuels (CMF) group of the IAPH

The IAPH Clean Marine Fuels Working Group aims to offer ship owners a broad range of alternative fuels to improve air quality and reduce gas emissions in and around harbours. The working group involves standardisation agencies, associations, classification societies, oil majors, bunker operators

⁶ World Ports Sustainability Program, "About", <https://sustainableworldports.org/about/>, last accessed October 2023

⁷ World Ports Sustainability Program, "WPCAP - WG 4 : Sustainable Marine Fuels – Our mission", <https://sustainableworldports.org/wpcap/wg-4/our-mission/>, last accessed October 2023

and ship owners. One of the main objectives of this working group is to develop practical tools to facilitate safe and efficient bunker operations in ports for existing and upcoming marine fuels⁸.

The CMF group together with the Sustainable Marine Fuels group developed a new tool – the Port Readiness Level indicator for Alternative Fuels for Ships (PRL-AFS). This tool allows to track the progress of ports offering port calls or bunkering services for alternative fuels. It offers transparency on port capabilities and development plans around fuel availability, bunkering infrastructure and vessel handling. It can also be used to map grouping of ports in specific regions which alternative fuels availability and associated bunkering capabilities⁹.

The CMF group also developed checklists for the bunkering of alternative marine fuels in ports including methanol. These checklists present the extra requirements with regards to bunker operations in or near the port environment. Two checklists were developed so far: one for ship-to-ship bunkering and another one for truck-to-ship bunkering. These checklists should contribute to a high level of quality of bunker operations¹⁰.

Getting to Zero Coalition of the Global Maritime Forum

The Getting to Zero Coalition is an industry-led alliance of more than 200 organizations from the maritime, energy and finance sectors supported by governments. The Coalition is committed to get deep sea zero emission vessel into operation by 2030 and to achieve full decarbonization of maritime transport by 2050. The coalition is managed by the global maritime forum which co-founded the alliance together with the World Economic Forum and Friends of Ocean Action¹¹. Fincantieri SI, a company of the Fincantieri group, and member of the Advisory Board Maersk are both members of the coalition.

The strategy 2022-2023 of the coalition is twofold: turn industry engagement into concrete action to develop green corridors, and support policy action especially regarding the adoption of the revised GHG strategy by the IMO. As part of its works, the grouping has developed a series of insight briefs and reports that highlight current challenges and opportunities. In June 2023, a report on green shipping corridors in and out of Spain was published¹².

⁸ World Ports Sustainability Program, “About our clean marine fuels working group”, <https://sustainableworldports.org/clean-marine-fuels/about-our-cmf-working-group/>, last accessed October 2023

⁹ World Ports Sustainability Program, “Port Readiness Level for Alternative Fuels for Ships”, [https://sustainableworldports.org/wpcap/wg-4/#:~:text=PRL%2DAFS%20indicator%20\(COMPLETED\)%3A,vessels%20using%20various%20alternative%20fuels.](https://sustainableworldports.org/wpcap/wg-4/#:~:text=PRL%2DAFS%20indicator%20(COMPLETED)%3A,vessels%20using%20various%20alternative%20fuels.), last accessed October 2023

¹⁰ World Ports Sustainability Program, “Bunker checklists”, <https://sustainableworldports.org/clean-marine-fuels/methanol-as-a-fuel/bunker-checklists/#tst>, last accessed October 2023

¹¹ Global maritime forum, “Getting to zero coalition”, <https://www.globalmaritimeforum.org/getting-to-zero-coalition>, last accessed October 2023

¹² Global maritime forum, “Green shipping corridors in and out of Spain: Assessing route-based opportunities”, <https://www.globalmaritimeforum.org/content/2023/06/Spanish-Green-Corridor.pdf>, last accessed October 2023

Renewable and Low-Carbon Fuels Value Chain Industrial Alliance

The Renewable and Low-Carbon Fuels (RLCF) Value Chain Industrial Alliance is a new initiative from the EU Commission that focuses on boosting production and supply of renewable and low-carbon fuels in the aviation and waterborne sectors. It is seen as a key supporting measure for FuelEU maritime and ReFuelEU aviation initiatives. The goal of this alliance is to safeguard that aviation and waterborne transport have sufficient access to renewable and low carbon fuels, to achieve a reduction of 90% of GHG in the transport sector by 2050.

The alliance was kicked off in 2022 with a first call for membership applications. The objectives and priorities have been developed in the first months of operation. The alliance should support the development of a pipeline of new projects in the aviation and waterborne sectors and help address common challenges and horizontal issues such as access to finance and access to feedstock¹³. Members defined a workplan and started to work together in four thematic roundtables:

- Roundtable 1: the availability of feedstocks, synergies among sectors and the so-called “just transition”,
- Roundtable 2: Production pathways and value chain – aviation,
- Roundtable 3: Production pathways and value chain – waterborne transport,
- Roundtable 4: Access to public and private finance¹⁴.

As of September 2023, the alliance counts 229 members with most of them being companies or industrial associations or initiatives. Member of the POSEIDON advisory board eFuel alliance is member of the RLCF alliance and co-chairs the first roundtable on feedstocks’ availability¹⁵. POSEIDON partner EDF participates in the roundtables 3 and 4.

eFuel Alliance (also member of the Advisory Board)

The eFuel alliance is committed to the promotion and expansion of the global production of synthetic carbon-neutral fuels and their widespread use in many sectors such as road, aviation and waterborne transport, the chemical industry and the heating sector instead of conventional heating fuels. The goal of the eFuel alliance is to gain political acceptance and regulatory approval for e-fuels as a measure to mitigate climate change¹⁶. The alliance is open to all organisations and interested parties and is made up of more than hundred companies and organisations from various industries.

¹³ EU Commission -Mobility and Transport, “Renewable and Low-Carbon Fuels Value Chain Industrial Alliance”, https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/clean-transport/alternative-fuels-sustainable-mobility-europe/renewable-and-low-carbon-fuels-value-chain-industrial-alliance_en, last accessed October 2023

¹⁴ RLCF alliance, “Roundtables kick-off meetings 21st and 22nd November – Highlight reports”, https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/clean-transport/alternative-fuels-sustainable-mobility-europe/renewable-and-low-carbon-fuels-value-chain-industrial-alliance_en, last accessed October 2023

¹⁵ RLCF alliance, “Alliance members as of 22nd September 2023”, https://transport.ec.europa.eu/transport-themes/clean-transport/alternative-fuels-sustainable-mobility-europe/renewable-and-low-carbon-fuels-value-chain-industrial-alliance_en, last accessed October 2023

¹⁶ eFuel alliance, “About the initiative”, <https://www.efuel-alliance.eu/initiative>, last accessed October 2023

It published many policy papers and joint statements to push the use of e-fuels in the maritime sector. Its political demands include the setting of minimum shares for hydrogen and eFuels – so-called renewable fuels of non-biological origin within the FuelEU Maritime regulation and the compensation for cost differences between renewable and fossil fuels to not disadvantage EU ports and shipowners¹⁷.

3 POSEIDON' USE CASES

This chapter presents the two use cases of POSEIDON: the use case of Thessaloniki exploring the process CO₂ route for e-methanol conversion and the use case of Valencia focusing on the biologic CO₂ conversion pathway.

¹⁷ eFuel Alliance, “eFuels in the shipping sector”, <https://www.efuel-alliance.eu/political-demands/maritime-sector>, last accessed October 2023

3.1 USE CASE THESSALONIKI

<p>Port’s characteristics</p> <table border="1"> <tr> <td>Port</td> <td>Thessaloniki</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sea basin</td> <td>Aegean Sea</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Port’s area</td> <td>1.5 km²</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Yearly cargo traffic</td> <td>7.3 million tons (2023)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Direct employment</td> <td>525</td> </tr> </table>		Port	Thessaloniki	Sea basin	Aegean Sea	Port’s area	1.5 km ²	Yearly cargo traffic	7.3 million tons (2023)	Direct employment	525	
Port	Thessaloniki											
Sea basin	Aegean Sea											
Port’s area	1.5 km ²											
Yearly cargo traffic	7.3 million tons (2023)											
Direct employment	525											
<p>Case study description</p> <p>Location of plant: The Thessaloniki case study consists of the CAO plant producing lime located in the greater port area, 10 km away from the port. The plant produces approximately 24,000 tons of CO₂ from limestone calcination and a total of 34,000 tons of CO₂ annually.</p> <p>E-methanol production capacity (estimated): About 14,000 tons/year of e-methanol could be produced if the 24,000 tons of CO₂ emitted from limestone calcination is transformed.</p> <p>Methanol off-takers: Exact ships to be converted and powered with e-methanol needs to be investigated. Potential locations for an e-methanol infrastructure at the piers of the port are already identified.</p>		<p>E-methanol plant characteristics</p> <p>Feedstock: CO₂ emissions come from the lime manufacturing process at the CAO’s plant and are either recovered from the exhaust gas emissions of the heat production unit or from so-called lime-off gas, a subproduct of CaCO₃ reaction. The technical options regarding water and energy supply for hydrogen production via electrolysis need to be investigated.</p> <p>Produced chemicals: the objective is to produce only e-methanol at CAO’s lime plant. The produced e-methanol will be transferred via tanker trucks or a pipeline and stored at the port and then be supplied via refuelling stations to e-methanol propelled vessels.</p>										
<p>Key activities to prepare the future implementation of the value chain</p> <p>It will be assessed which ships docking in the port can be converted to e-methanol and at what cost, and what their future demand will be. The feasibility of a power-to-methanol integration in a similar lime plant in Volos operated by affiliated partner Inventors will also be investigated. Furthermore, a specific task will be about studying innovative CO₂ capture technologies to be able to valorise CO₂ from industrial processes.</p>		<p>Long term ambition and vision</p> <p>This case study will help in assessing the potential of e-methanol production out of industrial and process CO₂. This is seen as an essential transition pathway until enough biogenic CO₂ is available and accessible for e-methanol production.</p>										

3.2 USE CASE VALENCIA

Port’s characteristics		
Port	Valencia	
Sea basin	Mediterranean Sea	
Port’s area	5.6 km ²	
Yearly cargo traffic	79 million tons (2022)	
Direct employment	17.973	
Case study description		E-methanol plant characteristics
<p>Location of plant: Two wastewater treatment plants operated by partner GOMSL located close to Valenciaport: Pinedo and Quart Benàger. Pinedo generates about 6,000 tons CO₂/year while Quart Benàger about 1,500 tons CO₂/year.</p> <p>E-methanol production capacity (estimated): about 5,600 tons of e-methanol per year could be produced with the ICODOS technology and the CO₂ from the biogas of the Pinedo and Quart Benàger plants.</p> <p>Methanol offtakers: the daily production would be sufficient to supply 3 tugboats operating in the port of Valencia at the Boluda tug terminal.</p>		<p>Feedstock: H₂ will be produced locally via an electrolyser supplied by local on-site power generation (solar PV) and additional renewable energy purchased on the market. Hydrogen will be stored and later fed to the ICODOS technology together with biogas resulting from the anaerobic digestion of sludge.</p> <p>Produced chemicals: biomethane that can either be fed into the gas grid, transformed in bio-LNG or burnt in CHP plants (the heat and power can be used on site) and renewable e-methanol that will be stored at the port of Valencia.</p>
Key activities to prepare the future implementation of the value chain		Long term ambition and vision
<p>The administrative and technical requirements for the ICODOS plant integration in Pinedo and Quart Benàger WWTPs will be thoroughly assessed by performing a HAZOP study. Furthermore, the e-fuel supply to the Port of Valencia and its use by tugboats will be investigated.</p>		<p>This case study should support the development of a new business activity – renewable fuel production - for wastewater treatment plants. Learnings will be shared with operators of other industrial or agricultural sites producing biogas.</p>

4 COPS WITHIN POSEIDON

4.1 MAIN TASKS ASSIGNED TO POSEIDON'S COPS

The COPS established within the project will have two main objectives:

1. Strengthen collaboration between members and be an open platform for knowledge exchange and transfer,
2. Prepare and support the post-project implementation of local value chains by co-developing selected project outputs and promoting them outside the COPS.

The Grant Agreement contains a list of to be implemented in the framework of the local COPS in Valencia and Thessaloniki by members of the COPS and project partners. The following non exhaustive list presents the main actions to be performed:

- **Community management** - Organize regular meetings to collect feedback and strengthen collaborations between members of the communities of practice,
- **Knowledge transfer** - Support capacity building of the COP members on the topic of renewable e-fuels via trainings and further dissemination measures,
- **Knowledge exchange** – Build the COP as trustful platform allowing for open discussions and the collection of needs and expectations of the main stakeholders. This is a prerequisite for COPS to sustain over time and achieve their objectives,
- **Co-creation and preparation of future steps** - Share non-sensitive research outputs with members of the COP to get their feedback. Project results that could benefit from co-development are for instance the scenario definition in task 2.5 and the development of the replication tool in WP6. COP members are also expected to contribute to the development and validation of local roadmaps and policy recommendations (both activities included in WP6),
- **Promotion of research results** - in line with the CDE strategy of POSEIDON; COPS will serve as dissemination platform and help in replicating the results to other locations in EU.

This list will serve as a first step for the development of a general workplan (see next subchapter) for the COPS to be established in Valencia and Thessaloniki.

4.2 PRELIMINARY COP WORKPLAN

The COP are expected to be kick-started by M6 and officially end by the end of the project. Nevertheless, COPS can continue in another form after the project ends and can for example become a working group for the implementation of the local value chains in real environments in Thessaloniki and Valencia. The following picture presents a preliminary workplan of COPS based on main tasks assigned and activities to be held by POSEIDON project partners to foster capacity building of COP members in renewable fuels. A detailed description of the workplan for each COP year is provided below.

Figure 2: Preliminary workplan of the COPs in Thessaloniki and Valencia

Year 1 (M6 – M12) – kick-off of COPs

Within the first project year, the COPs will be established in Valencia and Thessaloniki. It is expected that an in-person kick-off meeting will take place in the first project year at both locations. This first meeting will be very important since it will be the first time that COP members will meet. It will feature several presentations including a general presentation of the POSEIDON project, another one on the specific role of the COP, expected contributions and learning opportunities for COP members. A preliminary planning of the activities to be undertaken within the COPs will be shared and organizational details will be discussed based on outputs of this document. A second online meeting will be held towards M12. It should aim at consolidating the COPs's composition and identifying partners whose contributions are essential to ensure the success of the value chain implementation in Spain and Greece. This meeting will be combined with a short training on alternative fuels for shipping which will highlight the technologies to be developed within POSEIDON.

Year 2 (M13 – M24) – assessing needs and challenges

One of the key aspects to be deepened during the second year of the project are the needs of each COP member with regard to its business and the challenges imposed by the energy transition in general and more specifically by shipping industry transition towards greener fuels. It is foreseen that partners' inputs will be collected during a workshop (to be held during the first half of the second year) and that the results will be shared with partners involved in tasks 2.2 and 2.5, focusing on decarbonization strategies and associated challenges and the definition of scenarios respectively. Between M19 and M24, a cross-meeting gathering the partners of both COPs in Valencia and Thessaloniki will be held. This event will help in identifying similarities and differences between the two COPs and compare the selected scenarios for each of the use case for future assessment in WP5.

Year 3 (M25 – M36) – preliminary analysis of value chains

When the third year of the project will start, the COPs will be in cruise mode and members will have

already gained some knowledge of the POSEIDON project and of the topic of renewable fuels in shipping and the associated necessary value chain. The third project year will see the first results of the technoeconomic analysis and life cycle assessment studies. Preliminary results will be shared with COP members to collect feedback and validate some of the hypothesis and if applicable modify them to guarantee the soundness of the final evaluation results. M28 will mark the starting of the development of the replication tool. Members of the COPs will act as beta testers of the first versions of tool to be developed by lead partner EIFER (D6.3). They will help in improving the tool usability by giving inputs regarding the user interface and key features of the tool. Stakeholders of the COP are also expected to contribute to the market potential studies in WP6: ship operators and vessel builders could share information on their fleet and future plans regarding the use renewable fuels while feedstock providers could provide information on their capabilities to produce synthetic methanol at large scale.

Year 4 (M37 – M48) – policy workshops and future of COPs

The last year of POSEIDON is crucial to the future exploitation of results and will coincide with the fine tuning of the last project results. Two main results will be co-developed by project partners and members of the COPs: policy recommendations to improve the EU legal framework to widespread the use of synthetic methanol in shipping and the deployment of roadmaps outlining the post-project steps to be taken in Valencia and Thessaloniki to implement the investigated value chains in real industrial environments. Ideally, it would be a great achievement if members of the COP and interested stakeholders sign a memorandum of understanding towards project end to commit themselves to start implementing the action plans presented in the deployment roadmap just after the closure of POSEIDON. COP managers will prepare a survey to collect feedback on the almost 3,5 years operation of the COP and to see how the community of practice could be continued after project end. Results of this feedback will be compiled into D2.9 - Activity report of the Communities of practice to be drafted by partner Steinbeis. The learnings will be shared with the main stakeholders with the publication of a project guidebook and will be helpful to other ports, feedstock providers, vessel owners willing to launch their own new value chain based on synthetic methanol or participate in existing ones.

4.3 TARGETED COP MEMBERS

The external stakeholders who should become COP members are the main target groups of POSEIDON identified as such in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan (see deliverable 7.1). These targets groups consist of key industrial stakeholders positioned alongside the value chain such as feedstock providers, fuel suppliers and vessel operators. They also include public authorities and administrations, project developers, the EU research and development community, working groups focusing on the deployment of renewable fuels for shipping, standardization bodies and the general public. A description of the target groups and their primary interests regarding the implementation of local value chains based on e-methanol as fuel in shipping is provided in the following table.

Table 1: POSEIDON' main target groups who are targeted to become COP members

TG	Target group	Primary interests with regard the value chain to be implemented
TG1	Vessel operator	Comply with legislation, promote own green image, switch to renewable e-fuels available in large quantities which offer similar/better technical/economic performances than fossil ones
	Ship builders including engine manufacturers	Have renewable e-fuel available in sufficient quality and quantity requiring low maintenance and ensuring reliable operation
	Fuel suppliers including companies responsible for fuel logistics	Supply e-fuels with the guarantee of high quality, sufficient quantities and attractive price
TG2	Potential plant operators (companies, port authorities, ...)	Be able to easily deploy and run a power to e-methanol plant with low OPEX/CAPEX and low maintenance and service requirements ensuring short payback time
TG3	Feedstock providers (chemical companies, lime producers, wastewater treatment plant operators, biogas plant operators)	Comply with emissions regulations by reducing the CO ₂ footprint of the own business, and find ways to exploit unwanted emissions or by-products
	Energy utilities and energy companies providing renewable power	Support the decarbonisation of hard-to-electrify sectors and the integration of intermittent renewable sources while guaranteeing grid stability
TG4	Port operators / authorities and local authorities	Comply with legislation on zero emissions and decarbonisation and build infrastructure for renewable e-fuel bunkering
	Project developers, engineering offices and system integrators	Support the implementation of renewable e-fuel technologies by considering various requirements and selecting the most efficient technologies
TG5	EU research and scientific community	Initiate collaboration with industrial partners to progress SoA, contribute to education of future engineers and maintain EU scientific leadership in renewable e-fuels
TG6	Wider EU e-methanol community including associations, expert and interest groups, similar projects	Support the definition of standards and codes to ensure interoperability of novel technologies and build a community of followers to accelerate the transition towards green e-fuels in shipping
TG7	Policy makers and	Better understand benefits of renewable e-fuels in terms of

	standardisation/IP bodies	HSE and risks and develop and adopt regulations supporting decarbonisation targets and use of renewable e-fuels
TG8	General public / civil society	Broaden knowledge on renewable e-fuels and support initiatives promoting better air quality in harbour cities and low GHG emissions in transport

4.4 GENERAL METHODOLOGY TO DEVELOP COP FRAMEWORK

The methodology to develop COP framework is based on a playbook¹⁸ developed by the European Commission. This playbook can be used to assess an existing community or start a new one. In POSEIDON, it was used to create the framework of the local COPs in Thessaloniki and Valencia. The playbook covers different facets or success conditions of a COP to be met: the community should be driven with a clear vision and purpose (**Vision**), it should be steered by a good governance (**Governance**) and have the support of leaders taking key decisions (**Leadership**), the community should meet regularly and shared best practices, learn from each other through convened discussions (**Convening**) and actively cooperate to co-create results (**Collaboration and cooperation**). The community should have a manager (**Community management**) who makes the link between all members and invite them to online or in-person meetings. The community manger should also regularly check that members’ own and common interests are fulfilled (**User experience**) and that the community serves its goal by doing internal surveys and comparing results against planned agenda (**Measurement**).

Table 2: Facets of COP framework (based on EU playbook)

Success factor of community of practice	Description
Vision	A community needs a vision that has to correspond/contribute to the organisation’s vision and long-term goals. It needs a purpose expressing its raison d’être and a co-created vision that, in turn, has to be translated into SMART objectives.
Governance	A good governance framework is central to a well-functioning community. This starts with defining community membership via stakeholder mapping and continues with setting up meaningful structures (informal and formal) to take decisions and to ensure a risk-free environment.
Leadership	Community leadership is both about support, investment and participation from senior and middle management and about leadership from within the community. A core group of community members taking

¹⁸ EU Commission - JRC Publications Repository, “The Communities of Practice Playbook”, <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC122830>, last accessed February 2024

	the lead is a key element to steer the community through co-ownership
Convening	Convening is the art of (regularly) bringing the community together to keep engagement alive and connect community members in meaningful conversations. To convene meaningfully also means to regularly inject external expertise into the community and to ensure access and connections to other communities/networks/platforms.
Collaboration and cooperation	This is about working purposefully together towards delivering a concrete community deliverable. The more a community creates something concrete together, the more engaged it is: this requires effective coordination and co-creation methods.
Community management	A community cannot work without systematic community management. One of the main roles of the community manager is to facilitate the community interactions (both online and in person). In addition, he/she should act as meeting organiser, convener and knowledge exchange catalyst.
User experience	The community operational model should consider members’ needs and feedback. A user-centric experience with adapted structures, processes and tools is key to ensure that the COP sustains in the long run.
Measurement	Last but not least, measuring the community’s vitality and engagement is key to understanding what works in terms of practices that deliver on the objectives set, what does not work and what is necessary to understand better to improve the community

5 WORKSHOPS TO DEVELOP COP FRAMEWORK

5.1 SPECIFIC METHODOLOGY TO DEVELOP COP FRAMEWORK WITHIN POSEIDON

Based on the COP playbook presented in the previous chapter, partner Steinbeis developed a specific methodology to define the framework of the COPs in Valencia and Thessaloniki. Although the COPs in Spain and Greece share the same vision and purpose, their framework will differ due to the local context. To design these frameworks, partner Steinbeis designed one workshop that was presented to the community managers (FVP and ThPA) in December 2023. Later in January, COP community managers held a workshop with local stakeholders from Valencia and Thessaloniki. During these very first workshops, COP managers introduced the POSEIDON project, presented the COP concept and roles to be played by COP members and collected technical information on technical options to be investigated. After the workshops took place, a wrap-up meeting was held between the COP community managers and Steinbeis to discuss the results and prepare the next steps.

5.2 CONTENT/EXERCISES OF WORKSKOPS

The workshops involving project partners and local stakeholders were moderated by partners ThPA and FVP and focused on two main exercises: a first exercise dedicated to the identification and mapping of local stakeholders (see Annex 1 for further information) and a second one focusing on the definition of the essential characteristics (also called facets in the following) of a successful COP in Valencia and Thessaloniki based on local contexts and practices. This second exercise was performed using the following table that features for each key facet of a COP (=each line of the table) a possible option (considered as the more realistic by partner Steinbeis) and a list of open questions to be addressed by COP managers and workshop participants.

Table 3: Facets of COP framework adapted to POSEIDON project

Success factor of community of practice	Description
Vision	<p>Vision: Pave the way for the implementation of local value chains based on e-methanol as fuels in the ports of Valencia and Thessaloniki. The long-term goal is to speed up the uptake of renewable fuels in shipping in EU and have a network of EU ports equipped with a renewable fuel infrastructure and be a central value chain brick between production/import and transport/distribution and subsequent end use</p> <p>Mission/ Raison d'être: the community should gather stakeholders that are included in the local value chains and want to learn about renewable fuels in general and more specifically about the potentials of e-methanol. Through their involvement, they will increase their knowledge and investigate with the other members how a new value chain implementation can be realised and how they can benefit from it. An important aspect of the COP will be to ask members about their own interests and consider them when implementing activities</p>
	<p>Open question(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Are the vision and mission statements clear and shared by everyone or should we rephrase them?
Governance	<p>Possible governance structure: 1. a community manager who coordinates all actions, 2. a steering group consisting of local POSEIDON partners that have decision-making power and lead the whole community and 3. wider group consisting of all members</p>
	<p>Open question(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •What (governance) structure should be put in place? Are governance bodies necessary or should the hierarchical structure remain as flat as possible? •What are key features to build trust and motivate stakeholders to actively

	participate in the local COPs from a governance perspective?
Leadership	<p>Key stakeholders of the local value chains are identified in T2.1. The necessary political support and financial need required to implement the value chains in Thessaloniki and Valencia will be investigated. Based on this mapping, key stakeholders will be identified and invited to main events organized in the frame of the COPs. This should ensure that partners with decision-making power and funding capabilities are represented in the COPs.</p>
	<p>Open question(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Which communication strategy to be followed to best reach out to the whole community and get partners on board? •How to ensure strong leadership participation and make sure that decisions/strategies taken/developed within COP get support from high ranked decision makers? •How do you get your core group steer the whole community?
Convening	<p>At least 2 events will take place per year. A kick-off meeting will be held during the second half-year of POSEIDON. This meeting will present the POSEIDON project and its activities, the specific role of the COPs and its operational structure, the expected contributions and benefits for members and a preliminary timeline of events including milestones.</p>
	<p>Open question(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •What kind of events fit with your community in general? <p>Are there already working groups established within the port ecosystem that serve as platform of discussion for sustainability topics? (might be easier to re-use some of the existing platforms or advertise the COP within these platforms than to create new ones that may face a difficult start)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Which aspects/barriers such as language need to be considered when organising events? •How could collaboration with other national or EU networks dealing with similar networks be promoted? •Would exchanges between the COPs in Spain and Greece make sense?
Collaboration and cooperation	<p>In the first stage of the COPs, it will be essential to build trust and organise interesting events enabling participants to learn and share their needs while contributing marginally to the research outputs like the scenario definition within WP2. The second stage of the COP which is expected to start after M24 should mark the beginning of the co-development activities and local COP members should provide feedback regarding the impacts assessment study, the development of the replication tool and local roadmaps as well as the drafting of policy</p>

	<p>recommendations to boost the use of renewable fuels. Members' time investments will be rewarded with training courses on marine fuels, invitations to project events and the sharing of preliminary research results. It will be examined if the signature of an NDA is required to safeguard the confidentiality of results produced within POSEIDON.</p> <p>Open question(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •How to deal with confidentiality of information produced by POSEIDON? •Which results needs to be co-created and validated and how to best organise this collaboration considering confidentiality agreements?
<p>Community management</p>	<p>Open question(s):</p> <p>Two local community managers will oversee the COPs. The COP in Valencia will be coordinated by someone from Fundacion Valenciaport while the port in Thessaloniki ThPA will manage the COP in Thessaloniki. The first kick-off meeting should take place in person, and it is planned to set up a mailing list to facilitate the exchange of information. If deemed necessary, a MS sharepoint will be used to facilitate the sharing of documents. The role of the community manager will be to act as an intermediary between the project and the local members of the COPs. The manager will lead the steering group and will send invitations to meetings, prepare meetings together with partners of the steering groups (local project partners involved in task 2.3) and share regular news on the progress of the project or on upcoming dissemination events.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •What is the preferred way of interactions in person or online meetings? •If both ways are chosen, how to combine both and ensure that the flow of information between the 2 worlds is efficient?
<p>User experience</p>	<p>It will be important to organise short, concise, well-prepared meetings to keep members fully engaged throughout the project. The size of the group is an important aspect to consider: the group should not be too big (meaning not more than 30 people), thus allowing for sufficient space for discussions and knowledge exchanges so that every voice is heard. Regarding co-creation, the expectations must remain moderate. COP members who are not project partners will have little time to devote to proofreading documents. It will therefore be necessary to prepare targeted questions and collect feedback mainly orally.</p> <p>Open question(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •How to ensure good user experience and ensure that inputs and feedback from the membership are considered? •What (facilitation) methods can you use to encourage co-creation and make members cooperate and co-create?
<p>Measurement</p>	<p>It is planned to have a first measurement of the COP vitality at the end of the first year of COP activities towards M18. Members of the COPs will</p>

	<p>be asked to fill a short survey to collect feedback about the first year experience, the pros and cons, and activities they would like to see being implemented in the next years. Results of the survey will be used to amend the COP plans and improve the user experience. A final survey will be sent towards the end of the project.</p>
	<p>Open question(s):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Should regular survey be sent to members to assess the vitality of COPs and level of engagement of members?

5.3 WORKSHOP PROCESS

Preparation meeting in December 2023

The whole workshop process started with a first meeting involving partners Steinbeis, EIFER, FVP and ThPA at the end of December 2023. During this meeting, Steinbeis presented the main exercises to be carried out during the workshops to be held in January 2024 to collect information on local stakeholders and characteristics of COPs to be implemented in Valencia and Thessaloniki. COP managers FVP and ThPA were provided with a presentation and exercises to be performed with workshop participants. These exercises can be conducted using the visual work platform “Mural” which enables collaborative and creative work and the easy collection of ideas while working online.

In the remainder of this document, the workshop including Greek partners is referred to as the Greek workshop while the workshop involving Spanish partners is called Spanish workshop.

Greek workshop in January 2024

The Greek workshop was held on Thursday 11th January 2024. The online workshop was moderated by partner ThPA and gathered only Greek partners (project partners ThPA, AUTH, CERTH, CAO, INV and invited stakeholders). A wrap up meeting between ThPA, CERTH, AUTH, CAO, INV and partners Steinbeis and EIFER took place on January 23rd.

Table 4: Organisations external to the project that participated in the Greek workshop

Organisation	Type of activities
Danaos S.A.	Vessel operator/ maritime software technology providers
Motor Oil	Multinational company on oil refining and marketing of petroleum products
IRIS project	EU funded project on the construction and operation of a Carbon Capture, Utilisation and Storage (CCS) and e-methanol production system
Municipality of Thessaloniki	Public administration of the city of Thessaloniki

Prefecture of C. Macedonia	Public administration of the Central Macedonia region
Hellenic Ports Association (ELIME)	Union of Greek Ports
Greek Exporters Association	Association of exporting companies in Greece
HiRECORD project	Demonstration of advanced Rotating Packed Bed (RPB) capture plant at 3 industrial sites in Europe
PK-ENERGY	Engineering design and construction of renewable energy plants
DNV	Classification society
National Technical University of Athens – Dep. of Synthesis and Development of Industrial Processes	Marine Engineering: Ship Energy Systems analysis and optimisation
University of Piraeus – Dep. of Maritime Studies	Port and Terminal Policy and Management
EMICERT	Accredited GHG verifier for shipping emissions
ARGO NAVIS ENGINEERS	Engineering consultancy

A second internal online workshop took place on February 27th. It was moderated by COP manager ThPA. The picture below presents a screenshot of the meeting.

Figure 3: Screenshot taken during Greek online workshop on February 28th

Spanish workshop in January 2024

The Spanish workshop was held on Thursday 25th January 2024. It was an online workshop moderated by partner FVP and gathered only Spanish partners project partners (FVP, GOMSL, AVEBIOM and invited stakeholders). A wrap up meeting between FVP, GOMSL and partners Steinbeis and EIFER took place on January 30th.

Table 5: Organisations external to the project that participated in the Spanish workshop

Organisation	Type of activities
Fertiberia (participated on behalf of ASECAM)	Fertiliser manufacturer
Transportes Torres	Operator of fleets of trucks in main ports of the Spanish Peninsula
Balearia	Shipping company providing passenger ferry services
Unió Llauradora i Ramadera	Agricultural organization promoting the interests of farmers of the Valencian Community
Asociación de Investigación de la Industria Agroalimentaria (AINIA)	Research institute involved in several activities like chemistry, packaging, food, pharmacy, and cosmetics

Ajuntament de València	Public administration of the city of Valencia
Autoridad Portuaria de Valencia (APV)	Port authority of Valencia
Methanol Reformer	Manufacturer of solutions based on methanol reforming technologies
TEPSA	Terminal operator
Holcim (participated on behalf of ASECAM)	Concrete manufacturer
BP Energia	Multinational oil and gas company
Asociación Española de Empresas del Sector de la Energía (AVAESEN)	Valencian region cleantech Cluster
Generalitat Valenciana	Public administration of the Valencian Community
Asociación de Empresarios del Camp de Morvedre (ASECAM)	Association for the protection of employees' rights

Figure 4: Screenshot taken during Spanish online workshop on January 25th

5.4 MAIN RESULTS FROM GREEK WORKSHOP

Knowledge gaps of main stakeholders

The Greek workshop identified main knowledge gaps to be filled for the different target groups:

- Vessels’ operators, ship builders and fuel suppliers (TG1) will need information on e-methanol bunkering options and price and availability of e-methanol at given ports,
- Potential plant operators (TG2) are interested in the characteristics of the e-methanol plant from partner ICODOS to be able to plan new projects and derive business plans,

- Similarly, feedstock providers (TG3) wish to have additional information of the e-methanol production plant to investigate the integration of the plant in existing industrial processes and better understand which adaptations are necessary,
- Port operators, local public authorities and project developers (TG4) need to know more about the legislation around export and import of e-methanol, bunkering solutions for e-methanol as fuel in ports and energy systems necessary to power the e-methanol plant,
- The broader EU research community (TG5) is interested in innovations for the use of e-methanol in shipping such as e-methanol bunkering solutions,
- Similarly, the broader EU e-methanol community (TG6) wants to learn from new projects and have a better understanding of new technologies for e-methanol production, distribution and use in ships,
- Standardisation bodies (TG7) want to have a better knowledge of potential risks along the value chain to be able to develop safe standards that will ensure market uptake and public acceptance,
- The general public (TG8) is interested in the benefits of e-methanol at the local level in the city of Thessaloniki and what impact local e-methanol projects could have on air quality and health.

Placing of stakeholders in Power-Interest matrix

The second task of the Greek workshop was to categorize the stakeholders according to their power and interest in a future project focusing on the implementation of a value chain based on e-methanol in the port of Thessaloniki. The Power-Interest matrix consists of 4 cells:

- High power – High interest (top right): these stakeholders are likely to be the main players and decision makers that will have a considerable impact on the project success. It is key to manage the expectations of this group and work/engage with them,
- High power – Low interest (top left): these are stakeholders who hold power but are not interested in the outcome of the project. They need to be satisfied and kept informed, to avoid them using their power in a negative way, contrary to the project's objectives.
- Low power – High interest (bottom right): this group must be adequately informed through continuous dialogue. Stakeholders composing this group could become supporters of the project and be very helpful for the project success by providing inputs and feedback.
- Low power – Low interest (bottom left): these stakeholders only need to be informed of project progress from time to time. It is strategically wise to not invest too much effort in this group.

The results of the exercise are presented in the following picture.

Figure 5: Results of the Power-Interest matrix exercise for the Greek workshop

The matrix shows that most important stakeholders to consider for the Greek use case are vessel operators, ship builders, fuel suppliers and feedstock providers belonging to TG1 and TG3. These are the ones with high power and high interest. Port administrations, local authorities and standardization bodies (TG4 and TG7) are the main context setters that need to be kept informed while plant operator/solution providers (TG2) with less power should be consulted to check the technical feasibility of the project to be implemented in Thessaloniki. Other key stakeholders that are important for the future project implementation are the broader e-methanol community and EU research community (TG5 and TG6). They are considered "game changers" because of their role in developing new innovations and, as such, their activities will be closely monitored to take account of the latest technological advances and market trends. Their position in the matrix lies at the intersection of two categories. The general public will be at the heart of the communication strategy and get news on the project progress and its impact.

5.5 MAIN RESULTS FROM SPANISH WORKSHOP

Placing of stakeholders in Power-Interest matrix

As for the Greek workshop, stakeholders were positioned in the Power-Interest matrix by COP manager FVP. Like in the Greek workshop, partners operating all along the value chain were classified as most important partners to involve in COP activities. The stakeholders listed in the High Power – High Interest cell include tugboat operator Boluda, shipping company Balearia, operator of trucks TransTorres, concrete manufacturer Holcim, energy company BP, terminal operator TEPSA,

and Practicos in charge of harbour pilotage within port of Valencia (all belonging to TG1 and TG3). The stakeholders to keep satisfied are the main context setters, namely the port authority of Valencia (APV), the public administration of the Valencian community (Generalitat Valenciana) as well as the public administration of the city of Valencia (Ajuntament de Valencia). They belong to TG4 and TG7 respectively. The other identified stakeholders belong to the category Low Power-High Interest at the bottom right of the matrix. It includes technical partners and associations mostly from TG6 and from TG1 (solutions provider like Methanol reformer). Their full name and types of activities can be found in table 5. It will be key to keep these partners informed about the POSEIDON project and get them on board as supporters of the future implementation of a new value chain dedicated to e-methanol in Valencia and its region.

Figure 6: Results of the Power-Interest matrix exercise for the Spanish workshop (results shows as organization names)

The following figure presents the results of the Spanish workshop with target groups instead of organization names. This graph provides a better comparison of the results of the two workshops and reveals that the results of the stakeholder mapping are very similar for both workshops. The most important stakeholders to manage closely are feedstock suppliers and end-users, followed in order of importance by local administrations and port authorities; local associations and similar projects; the EU research community; standardization bodies; potential plant operators and project developers; and finally, the general public.

Figure 7: Results of the Power-Interest matrix exercise for the Spanish workshop (results shown as target groups)

6 CONCLUSION

This last chapter summarizes the main characteristics of the COPs to be formed in Valencia and Thessaloniki as part of the POSEIDON project based on outcomes of workshops held in January 2024. It should be noted that the definition of the COP framework is an evolving process and that some of the aspects described in the next subchapter are subject to change because of feedback collection and project learnings. All changes to the COP framework and to the workplan of COPs will be summarized in the technical reports to be submitted to the European Commission at the end of the reporting periods. A general summary of all COP activities will be provided in D2.9 - Activity report of the Communities of practice to be submitted in M46 by partner Steinbeis.

6.1 COP FRAMEWORK FOR POSEIDON

Based on the results the workshops and discussions held between EIFER, Steinbeis and the local COP managers FVP and ThPA, the following COP framework was defined. It covers the 8 main facets described in the Communities of Practice Playbook of the EU Commission (see chapter 4.4). The presented COP framework applies for both COPs to be implemented in Valencia and Thessaloniki since discussions showed that local contexts are very similar. However, it is possible that differences may arise between the two COPs during the course of the project, which will then lead to small adjustments of COP frameworks.

Vision

- The long-term vision is the implementation of local value chains based on e-methanol as fuels in the ports of Valencia and Thessaloniki after project closure based on POSEIDON' research outputs.
- The formation of local COPs should support this vision by enabling COP members to acquire strategic capabilities for future value chain implementation and lay the foundations for a future project team willing to continue the vision once POSEIDON is finished.
- The POSEIDON project will benefit from the knowledge of local COPs members: the co-development of results will guarantee the soundness of project results and support the public acceptance of key players positioned along the value chain.

Governance

- The COP management will be led by partners FVP, manager of the Spanish COP, and ThPA, manager of the Greek COP, and supported by Spanish and Greek project partners respectively.
- Steinbeis will act as facilitator of COP activities by supporting the preparation of content and by ensuring the link between the COP managers and the POSEIDON consortium (especially all tasks outside WP2 that should benefit from the COP feedback).
- EIFER as coordinator and WP2 leader will duly monitor the COP activities and make the link with other WP2 tasks.

Leadership

- The identification and mapping of key stakeholders was done as part of first workshop exercise.
- The partners identified in the power-interest matrix as being key partners for the implementation of the value chain will be contacted as a priority to participate in the COP. This corresponds primarily to partners positioned in the top line of the Power-Interest matrix (partners having power) but can also be extended to partners with low power but highly interested in shaping the future implementation project. It will be ensured that partners that will not join the COP will be able to follow the COP activities from afar (see next point).
- If some members do not want to be actively involved due to time and resource constraints, efforts will be made to keep them informed about the project progress and main achievements and decisions through targeted communication activities.

Convening

- The objective in terms of convening is to have at least 1, ideally 2 meetings a year (either online or in person). A preliminary list of activities is presented in Figure 2.
- It is planned to organise at least one cross meeting between the two COPs to promote knowledge exchange and compare the two-value chain scenarios and considered approaches.
- If deemed applicable and feasible, COP meetings can be merged with existing locally active

knowledge platforms to exploit synergies and avoid overloading COP members' calendars.

Collaboration and Cooperation

- Co-creation is considered for some research outputs such as the definition of value chain scenarios, the development of deployment roadmaps, policy recommendations and replication tools.
- The COP will be designed as an open discussion and exchange platform that should be an attractive platform to join for external stakeholders with as few barriers to entry as possible. Co-creation activities will be done in such a way that non-confidential or sensitive information is shared by project partners with COP members. In such a way, COP members won't be required to sign an NDA.
- If in some cases, it appears that the exchange of confidential or sensitive information is deemed essential, then COP member(s) involved in the exchange of information will be requested to sign an NDA. However, this measure should only be applied as a last resort.

Community management

- FVP and ThPA will act as COP managers and coordinate all main COP activities at local level. Having COP managers speaking the same language as COP members and well connected in their respective networks, will help win over new members and reduce language barriers.

User experience

- Participation in COP should represent a win-win situation for all parties involved (external stakeholders/COP members and POSEIDON project partners). A balance needs to be found between 1. learning activities benefiting COP members that would like to learn more on e-methanol and the associated value chain to embark on a new value chain and business model and 2. more project-oriented activities benefiting primarily the project and its partners.
- Project oriented activities such as the review of preliminary results will be designed in such a way that they meet the principle of low time investment so that participation in COP does not become an additional workload for its members. If deemed relevant, online tools such as Mural will be used to collect feedback and jointly create ideas.

Measurement

- Two surveys will be sent to COP members: one at project midterm (around M24-M30) and one towards the end of the project. These surveys will be designed by partner Steinbeis and validated and sent by both COP managers FVP and ThPA.
- Mid-term survey results will be used to amend the COP framework and workplan to best fit COPs' members expectations and ensure long term buy-in.

6.2 NEXT STEPS

Now that a general COP framework is available, the next step will be to kick off the COPs by having a first meeting with interested parties. The kick-off of the Spanish COP will happen on Wednesday March 6th at the end of the second consortium meeting in Valencia. Partners Steinbeis and EIFER supported by local COP manager FVP will, during a one-hour meeting, present the POSEIDON project, introduce the concept of COP and expected role of COP members and respond to open questions. This first exchange between the POSEIDON project management and the potential future members of the COP should help to build a trust relationship between both parties and formalise the official start of a 3,5-year continuous exchange based on mutual learnings lasting until project end. A similar kick-off meeting is planned for the Greek COP. An online meeting will take place in April 2024 and an in-person meeting should take place in September 2024 in conjunction with the third consortium meeting in Greece.

7 ANNEX

ANNEX 1 – EXERCISES OF WORKSHOP FOCUSSED ON STAKEHOLDER IDENTIFICATION AND MAPPING

The workshop on stakeholder identification and mapping consisted of three main exercises that are presented below.

Exercise 1 – Mapping of stakeholders

TG	Target group	Local stakeholders operating at use case/regional level
TG1	Vessel operator	
	Ship builders including engine manufacturers	
	Fuel suppliers	
TG2	Potential plant operators (companies, port authorities, ...)	
TG3	Feedstock providers (chemical companies, lime producers, wastewater treatment plant operators, biogas plant operators)	
	Energy utilities and energy companies providing renewable power	
TG4	Port operators/authorities and local authorities	
TG4	Project developers, engineering offices and system integrators	
TG5	EU research and scientific community	
TG6	Wider EU e-methanol community including associations, expert and interest groups, similar projects	
TG7	Policy makers and standardisation/IP bodies	
TG8	General public / civil society	

Exercise 2 – Mapping of stakeholders’ primary interests

TG	Target group	Primary interests with regard the value chain to be implemented
	Vessel operator	
TG1	Ship builders including engine manufacturers	
	Fuel suppliers	
TG2	Potential plant operators (companies, port authorities, ...)	
TG3	Feedstock providers (chemical companies, lime producers, wastewater treatment plant operators, biogas plant operators)	
	Energy utilities and energy companies providing renewable power	
TG4	Port operators/authorities and local authorities	
	Project developers, engineering offices and system integrators	
TG5	EU research and scientific community	
TG6	Wider EU e-methanol community including associations, expert and interest groups, similar projects	
TG7	Policy makers and standardisation/IP bodies	
TG8	General public/ civil society	

Exercise 3 – Positioning of stakeholders in the Power-Interest matrix

